

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Resilience-Based Employee Performance Improvement Model at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar

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Abstract

The research was conducted at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar, which is one of the restaurants in Gianyar with its flagship product, duck dishes. As a restaurant, of course, the service provided must be able to satisfy consumers. So it requires employees who are able to work optimally to realize this. The research used a quantitative descriptive design, with the research location at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar. The research population was all employees of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar as many as 50 people, with a saturated sampling technique so that the entire population was sampled. Data were analyzed using the Partial Least Square (PLS) statistical method. The results of the study showed that work motivation and employee competence had a positive and significant effect on employee resilience and employee performance, resilience had a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar. It is recommended to Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar to improve cooperation between employees so that they can work together as a team to provide input to each other in completing work, as well as improve the training provided to employees so that employee competence is further improved and produces more optimal performance.

Keywords: Work Motivation; Competence; Resilience; Employee Performance

1. Introduction

Restaurants are no longer just places to satisfy basic food needs, but also platforms for cultural expression, social interaction, and unforgettable experiences. The digitalization trend is also impacting the restaurant industry, with more and more restaurants utilizing social media, online apps, and digital ordering systems to reach customers and improve operational efficiency. Restaurants that are able to adapt to these changes have a greater chance of success and maintaining their competitiveness. However, along with this growth, the restaurant industry also faces complex challenges, including intense competition, fluctuating raw material prices, difficulties in maintaining service quality, and high employee turnover.

To provide satisfactory service to customers, a restaurant requires employees who are able to demonstrate their best performance at work and are responsible for their work (1). However, in fact, employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar have not been able to demonstrate maximum performance. This is evident from the many consumer complaints on Google Reviews Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar who expressed dissatisfaction with the length of time consumers have to wait for their ordered menu to be served, so it seems that employees have not been able to maximize their performance to provide satisfaction to consumers, especially in terms of service.

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To predict and understand the factors influencing employee performance, this study will utilize Social Cognitive Theory developed by Albert Bandura (2). This theory states that individual behavior is shaped through the reciprocal interaction between personal factors such as thoughts, beliefs, emotions, the social environment, and concrete actions. In the workplace context, this means that employee performance is determined not only by external factors such as work systems or leadership, but also by internal factors such as self-confidence, motivation, and other personal capacities. An individual's belief in their abilities plays a crucial role in how they respond to work challenges, set goals, and maintain enthusiasm in difficult situations. Therefore, self-confidence is an important foundation that influences productive and resilient work behavior.

During the research process, a pre-survey was also conducted via Google Form with ten employee representatives of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar regarding employee complaints towards the company that caused low employee motivation in working. This was to find out about employee perceptions and experiences during work so that they can provide an overview of the challenges faced by employees during work. Based on the results of the highest pre-survey, it showed that employees agreed that the workload was too high which made employees less motivated in working. Second, external factors such as economic conditions and competition. Third, not being given appreciation by superiors and coworkers and the lack of balance between work and personal life that was not maintained made employee motivation to work decrease.

In such circumstances, resilience becomes crucial for employees. Resilience is the ability to adapt and remain steadfast in difficult circumstances (3). Resilience is necessary for employees to remain resilient and provide excellent service when faced with emotions and complaints from customers, which can potentially create an unpleasant work environment. This situation is further exacerbated by conflicts with coworkers or superiors, which can impact employee performance. Employee competencies also play a crucial role in determining the quality of employee performance. Unfortunately, a phenomenon observed at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, indicates that some employees lack enthusiasm for learning new things, which in turn hinders the development of skills relevant to job demands. Based on this explanation, this research is very important to be carried out in order to improve the business development of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar by improving employee performance in providing service to consumers.

This study aimed to determine the influence of work motivation and employee competence on performance through employee resilience at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. The results of this study are expected to produce a comprehensive and empirically tested model, which is not only relevant to Bebek Uma Sari Resto but also provides a significant contribution to the development of human resource management science, particularly in the context of the dynamic restaurant industry.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Employee Performance

Employee performance is something that is assessed from what an employee does in their work, in other words, individual performance is how an employee carries out their work or for their work (4). Performance is something that people actually do and can be observed, performance includes actions and behaviors that are relevant to organizational goals, performance is not a consequence or result of an action, but the action itself (5). Employee performance can be a benchmark to measure how much positive work results an employee brings to the organization (6).

2.2. Work Motivation

Work motivation is to provide a driving force that can foster employee enthusiasm for work so that they are willing to cooperate and work well, and unite all their efforts to achieve satisfaction, the existence of work motivation can be an encouragement for someone to do work (7). Work motivation is something that drives employees both from within and from outside the employee, as a result the employee has great passion, will and ambition and will make a big contribution to the success of achieving goals according to (8).

2.3. Competence

Competency is knowledge or know-how for doing an affective job. Competency is a basic characteristic that correlates of individual or team performance achievement (9). Competence is generally defined as skill, ability, and capability (10). Higher employee competency will also result in higher employee performance, which is because competence is the driving force of performance, the high or low quality of performance, and the good or bad performance of the implementation of certain activities (11).

2.4. Resilience

Resilience is the ability to overcome and adapt to difficult events or problems in life (12). In line with this, Aminah and Santi stated that resilience is the human ability to face, overcome, and learn from life's difficulties and bad experiences that have been experienced (13). Resilience is related to how individuals and organizations continue to achieve the desired results despite facing difficulties and pressures in work or in organizations (14).

2.5. Research Gap

Although there have been several studies examining employee performance related to influencing factors such as work motivation and employee competencies, there are still similarities, namely there is still very little relationship with employee resilience, each individual has their own problems, but how the individual survives in facing personal and work life situations is very important to be linked to the inherent performance of the employee in the company. On the other hand, many previous studies have focused on manufacturing companies and there are still few studies examining the service industry sector, especially restaurants, where employees must be able to handle consumer complaints directly which can make the work atmosphere less comfortable, while at the same time must still be able to provide satisfactory service to other consumers.

2.6. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the resilience-based employee performance improvement model at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar, can be presented in the following figure 1.

Source: processed by Author

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2.7. Hypothesis of Research

- H1: Work motivation has a positive effect on employee resilience
- H2: Work motivation has a positive effect on employee performance
- H3: Competence has a positive effect on employee resilience
- H4: Competence has a positive effect on employee performance
- H5: Resilience has a positive effect on employee performance

2.8. Method

This study uses a quantitative descriptive design, with the research location at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar. The research population was all 50 employees of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar, the sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with saturated sampling technique or total sampling. The research data based on its nature consists of quantitative data from the results of questionnaire distribution, and qualitative data in the form of company data and presentation of the results of questionnaire distribution data. Based on its source, it consists of primary data in the form of observation results and questionnaire distribution, as well as secondary data in the form of data and records from company archives.

Data collection was conducted through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and research documentation. Questionnaire data were scored using a Linkert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Data were

analyzed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) statistical method with the help of the SEM PLS 3.0 program. Data analysis began with descriptive analysis, which is research conducted to determine the existence of independent variables, whether one or more variables, without making comparisons or linking them to other variables (15). Next, a Structural Equation Model Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) analysis was performed, which yielded the following equation:

Substructure 1:

$$M = \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + e$$

Substructure 2:

$$Y = \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3M + e$$

Where:

Y = Dependent Variable (Employee Performance)

M = Mediator Variable (Resilience)

X1 = Independent Variable (Work Motivation)

X2 = Independent Variable (Competence)

e = residual value/standard error

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Outer Model Evaluation (Measurement Model)

3.1.1. Convergent Validity

Table 1 Outer Loading Value of Model Estimation Results

Indicator	Outer Loading	P Values	Explanation
Y1.1 <- Resilience (Y1.1)	0,923	0,000	Valid
Y1.2 <- Resilience (Y1.2)	0,903	0,000	Valid
Y1.3 <- Resilience (Y1.3)	0,816	0,000	Valid
X1.1 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,545	0,004	Valid
X1.2 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,809	0,000	Valid
X1.3 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,503	0,000	Valid
X1.4 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,594	0,002	Valid
X1.5 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,832	0,000	Valid
X1.6 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,862	0,000	Valid
X1.7 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,604	0,000	Valid
X1.8 <- Work motivation (X1)	0,803	0,000	Valid
X2.1 <- Competence (X2)	0,744	0,000	Valid
X2.2 <- Competence (X2)	0,686	0,000	Valid
X2.3 <- Competence (X2)	0,849	0,000	Valid
X2.4 <- Competence (X2)	0,803	0,000	Valid
X2.5 <- Competence (X2)	0,786	0,000	Valid
Y2.1 <- Employee performance (Y2.1)	0,830	0,000	Valid
Y2.2 <- Employee performance (Y2.2)	0,810	0,000	Valid
Y2.3 <- Employee performance (Y2.3)	0,913	0,000	Valid
Y2.4 <- Employee performance (Y2.4)	0,757	0,000	Valid

Y2.5 <- Employee performance (Y2.5)	0,612	0,001	Valid
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Source: processed field data

The outer loading calculation results for each variable's indicators showed an outer loading value > 0.50 and a p-value < 0.05. This proves that the indicators forming the latent variable are valid and significant.

3.1.2. Discriminant Validity

Table 2 Cross Loading Calculation Results

	Employee performance (Y2)	Competence (X2)	Work motivation (X1)	Resilience (Y1)
Y1.1	0,602	0,800	0,552	0,924
Y1.2	0,583	0,770	0,529	0,918
Y1.3	0,878	0,802	0,633	0,803
X1.1	0,632	0,520	0,857	0,463
X1.2	0,653	0,631	0,850	0,606
X1.3	0,504	0,373	0,707	0,399
X1.4	0,746	0,687	0,831	0,636
X1.5	0,675	0,527	0,876	0,511
X1.6	0,649	0,623	0,841	0,579
X1.7	0,525	0,419	0,705	0,365
X1.8	0,755	0,663	0,850	0,642
X2.1	0,872	0,762	0,658	0,641
X2.2	0,682	0,730	0,477	0,559
X2.3	0,669	0,876	0,604	0,914
X2.4	0,506	0,782	0,496	0,815
X2.5	0,696	0,783	0,478	0,595
Y2.1	0,894	0,746	0,676	0,646
Y2.2	0,819	0,786	0,545	0,744
Y2.3	0,849	0,710	0,725	0,639
Y2.4	0,739	0,651	0,496	0,585
Y2.5	0,737	0,632	0,763	0,616

Source: processed field data

The results of the loading factor calculations for each indicator of employee performance constructs, work motivation, competence, and resilience have the highest loading factor for the intended construct compared to the loading factor and are declared valid.

Table 3 Calculation Results √ AVE and Correlation Values Between Variables

Construct	AVE	Coefficient Correlation			
		Y2	X2	X1	Y1
Employee performance (Y2)	0,656	0,810	0,810		
Competence (X2)	0,621	0,788	0,872	0,788	

Work motivation (X1)	0,668	0,817	0,797	0,695	0,817
Resilience (Y1)	0,780	0,910	0,799	0,903	0,657

Source: processed field data

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for all constructs is > 0.50, thus fulfilling the validity requirements based on the discriminant validity criteria.

3.1.3. Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

Table 4 Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha Test

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability
Employee performance (Y2)	0,867	0,872	0,905
Competence (X2)	0,846	0,854	0,891
Work motivation (X1)	0,929	0,938	0,941
Resilience (Y1)	0,858	0,859	0,914

Source: processed field data

The composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha values of all constructs have shown values greater than 0.70, thus fulfilling the reliable requirements based on the composite reliability criteria.

3.2. Inner Model Evaluation (Structural Model)

3.2.1. R-Square (R2)

Table 5 R-Square (R2)

Construct	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee performance (Y2)	0,831	0,820
Resilience (Y1)	0,817	0,809

Source: processed field data

The R2 value of employee performance is 0.820; the model is included in the strong model criteria, meaning that variations in competency and work motivation are able to explain variations in employee performance by 82.0 percent, the remaining 18.0 percent is explained by variations in other variables. Meanwhile, the resilience variable has an R-square value of 0.809 or is included in the strong model, meaning that variations in work motivation, competency, and resilience are able to explain employee performance by 80.9 percent, the remaining 19.1 percent is explained by variations in other constructs outside the model.

3.2.2. Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q2)

The Q2 calculation results show that a value of 0.9656 (96.56%) can be explained through the relationship between employee performance, work motivation, competence, and resilience variables, while the remaining 3.44% is due to other factors outside the research model. Based on these results, the estimated global model is included in the strong criteria.

3.2.3. Goodness of Fit (GoF)

The calculation results show a Goodness of Fit (GoF) value of 0.75, so referring to the criteria for the strength and weakness of the measurement model through Goodness of Fit (GoF) according to Hair (15), this research model is classified as a strong (large) model.

3.3. Hypothesis Test

Measurement of the relationship between variables or models is predicted using the t-test parameter and to explain the hypothesis, it can be seen from the significance value of the comparison of the t-table value with the calculated t-value at a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (alpha 95%). The decision-making criteria for the t-test are H0 is accepted if: P-value \geq

0.05 and H1 is accepted if: P-value \leq 0.05. In terms of testing hypotheses, the results of SmartPLS 3.0 data processing are displayed in the form of images, as shown in Figure 2 as follows:

Source: processed field data

Figure 2 Path Diagram

Table 6 Path Analysis

Construct	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Explanation
Work Motivation (X1) -> Resilience (Y1)	0,346	2,747	0,006	Significant
Work Motivation (X1) -> Work Motivation (Y2)	0,374	2,616	0,009	Significant
Competence (X2) -> Resilience (Y1)	0,573	4,186	0,000	Significant
Competence (X2) -> Work performance (Y2)	0,592	4,143	0,000	Significant
Resilience (Y1) -> Work performance (Y2)	0,452	3,183	0,002	Significant

Source: processed field data

The test of the path coefficient between work motivation and the resilience construct was 0.346 with a t-statistic coefficient of 2.747 > t-table 1.96, and a significance value of 0.006 < 0.05, indicating that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on resilience. The results of this test prove the first hypothesis (H1), which states that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee resilience at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar, can be accepted.

The path coefficient between work motivation and employee performance was 0.374, with a t-statistic of 2.616 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.009 < 0.05, indicating that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. These test results support the second hypothesis (H2), which states that work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar.

The path coefficient between competency and the resilience construct was 0.573, with a t-statistic of 4.186 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating that competency has a positive and significant influence on resilience. The results of this test prove that the third hypothesis (H3), which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on the resilience of Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees, Singapadu Gianyar, can be accepted.

The path coefficient between competency and the employee performance construct was 0.592, with a t-statistic coefficient of 4.143 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating that competency has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. These test results support the fourth hypothesis (H4), which states that competency has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, and is accepted.

The path coefficient between resilience and the employee performance construct was 0.452, with a t-statistic coefficient of 3.183 > 1.96, and a significance value of 0.002 < 0.05, indicating that resilience has a positive and significant influence

on employee performance. The results of this test prove that the fourth hypothesis (H4), which states that resilience has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar, can be accepted.

Table 7 Total Indirect Effect

Construct	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Explanation
Work Motivation (X1) -> Resilience (Y1) -> Work performance (Y2)	0,156	2,012	0,045	Significant
Competence (X2) -> Resilience (Y1) -> Work performance (Y2)	0,259	2,648	0,008	Significant

Source: processed field data

The test results for the path coefficient between work motivation and employee performance, mediated by resilience, were 0.156, with a t-statistic coefficient of 2.012 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value of 0.045 < 0.05. The test results prove that resilience positively and significantly mediates the influence of work motivation on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar.

The test results for the path coefficient between competence and employee performance, mediated by resilience, were 0.259, with a t-statistic coefficient of 2.648 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value of 0.008 < 0.05. The test results prove that resilience positively and significantly mediates the influence of competence on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar.

4. Discussion

The results of this test confirm the first hypothesis (H1), which states that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee resilience at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. This means that the higher the work motivation, the higher the employee's resilience. Work motivation is a driving factor that can generate employee enthusiasm to perform optimally. This indicates that work motivation is a crucial foundation for building employee resilience. Social Cognitive Theory, developed by Albert Bandura (2), states that internal factors such as work motivation significantly determine the actions employees take in various work situations. Highly motivated employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, tend to be more resilient in the face of challenges that arise in the company environment. This demonstrates that work motivation significantly influences employee resilience. Motivation is a fundamental element that shapes employees' ability to survive and adapt better.

The results of this test confirm the second hypothesis (H2), which states that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. This means that the higher the work motivation of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, the higher their performance will be. Motivation is an effort that can encourage someone to take a desired action. Motivation functions as a driving force or impetus for employees to work diligently to achieve company goals. Based on Albert Bandura's (2) Social Cognitive Theory, internal factors within employees, such as high self-motivation, can increase employee enthusiasm for work and determine their response to work challenges. Therefore, employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, with high motivation, can complete every task with enthusiasm and result in better performance.

The results of this test confirm the third hypothesis (H3), which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee resilience at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. This means that the higher the employee's competence, the higher their resilience. Competence, in the context of resilience, refers to the knowledge and skills an individual possesses that can help improve their ability to cope with stress or unpleasant situations. Social Cognitive Theory, developed by Albert Bandura (2), states that an individual's belief in their abilities plays a crucial role in how they respond to work challenges, set goals, and maintain enthusiasm in difficult situations. Employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, who possess strong competence—a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes relevant to their job and work environment—tend to have higher levels of resilience. This means they can persevere and remain effective even when faced with challenges or stress. Competence is not only about what the employees of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar know in terms of knowledge, but also how they are able to apply that knowledge in their daily work practices in the field of skills.

The results of this test confirm the fourth hypothesis (H4), which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. This means that the higher the competence of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, the higher their performance will be. Competence influences employee performance. An employee with high competence, such as knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes appropriate to their position, is always motivated to work effectively, efficiently, and productively. This occurs because the employee's competence enhances their ability to carry out assigned tasks. Social Cognitive Theory, developed by Albert Bandura (2), states that self-confidence is a crucial foundation influencing productive and resilient work behavior. Self-confidence arises from an individual's high level of skill. Competence is the driving force behind performance, determining the quality of performance, and determining the success or failure of a particular activity. If the competency of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar employees regarding motives, character, self-concept, knowledge and skills increases, then the performance of Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar employees will also increase.

The results of this test confirm the fourth hypothesis (H4), which states that resilience has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. This means that the higher the resilience of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, the higher their performance will be. Resilience is a crucial quality that every employee should possess. By possessing resilience, an individual is able to overcome obstacles or challenges that arise in the workplace, recover, and return to productivity after facing difficulties. Based on Social Cognitive Theory developed by Albert Bandura (2), individual behavior is shaped through the reciprocal interaction of personal factors such as thoughts, beliefs, emotions, the social environment, and concrete actions. The ability to withstand and recover from work pressure strengthens employees and provides valuable experience to improve their work performance. There is a very close relationship between resilience and employee performance at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. Resilience helps Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees in the learning and self-development process. When Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees in Singapadu, Gianyar are able to quickly overcome stress, pressure, or failure, they will be more easily able to adapt to various changes or new challenges that exist in the work environment.

5. Conclusion

The conclusions related to the resilience-based employee performance improvement model at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar, in this study are: good work motivation will increase the resilience of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. Good work motivation will also improve the performance of employees at Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu, Gianyar. High competence will increase the resilience of Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees in Singapadu, Gianyar. High competence will also improve the performance of Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees in Singapadu, Gianyar. Good employee resilience will improve the performance of Bebek Uma Sari Resto employees in Singapadu, Gianyar.

The results of this study can provide input to Bebek Uma Sari Resto, Singapadu Gianyar to make improvements and enhancements to aspects that are deemed to be less than ideal based on the results of this study, so that each employee can provide maximum and satisfactory performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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